

THE IMPORTANCE OF ENGLISH IN THE MODERN WORLD

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Abstract:

Keywords:

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

To communicate with individuals completely different nationalities and from different countries within the world, many international languages area unit used. Among them, the foremost common language was English. After all, English isn't simply a language spoken within the USA and also the Great Britain. Firstly, Ireland, Canada, Australia, New Island, several African countries and individual Asian states is additional here. Secondly, it's quite simply the language of individual countries.

English has been selected because the language of negotiation in international organizations like the international organization General Assembly, the European Security Alliance, UNESCO, NATO, the European Union and also the Organization of the rock oil commercialism Countries (OPEC).

The Importance of English within the present time

Society has repeatedly tried to seek out an alternate to the English language. This was tired order to equalize the possibilities of representatives of various nations in learning a remote language. These makes an attempt semiconductor diode to the creation of many new languages, among that artificial language became the foremost common.

The author of "Esperanto" is Lazer Markovich Zamenhof, a linguist from Warsaw. The language was created in 1887, it took the author ten years to develop it. However, at a particular purpose, development and popularization delayed considerably.

Presumably, the explanation for this was that the by artificial means created language has no history, whereas English encompasses a made history and deep roots. After all, it absolutely was spoken, sung and written by nice musicians,

poets, philosophers.

That is why nowadays international summits and negotiations area unit command in English, the study of the planet expertise of colleagues in numerous fields and areas, necessary state documents area unit signed, conferences of presidents of various countries. International trade relations area unit conducted in English, the work of the money and transport systems is dole out.

The role of the English language within the present time is basically nice. It's studied in faculties, universities, specialised English courses on-line and offline. Because of the progress within the field of digital technologies, everybody will learn a global language while not departure home. And such associate approach in fashionable society is taken into account not simply the norm, however a necessity.

And this is often despite the decent grammatical, morphological and lexical quality of English for USA. After all, compared with the Russian language, English implies strict observance of the order of words once collecting sentences, and also the structure of the language itself, though similar (unlike an equivalent Chinese), still has several variations.

English belongs to the cluster of Germanic languages of the natural language family. The quantity of individuals (native speakers) for whom English is native is concerning 600 million people. The quantity of individuals WHO speak English is over 1.5 billion.

The connection of learning English

Do you speak English? - this is often the expression that may most frequently be detected from individuals from completely different countries WHO try to seek out a "common" language. And once associate affirmative "Yes" sounds in response, active communication begins between strangers.

Spheres and directions within the world within which English is that the solely language for communication:

The world of science - scientific conferences and discussion of worldwide world issues, exchange of expertise and necessary scientific data, writing scientific papers and works;

Sports field - all international sports competitions (Olympic Games, international starts, championships).

Traveling - it's not possible to grasp the languages of all countries and peoples, however it's enough to grasp English to travel round the world with none issues and communicate with representatives of different nations;

Employment - information of English can assist you quickly and simply get the required position in a very giant foreign company in any country.

The field of education is to induce a prestigious education within the best instructional establishments in Europe and America.

The sphere of cinema and literature - English makes it easier to observe films and browse classic literature within the original.

Every person is keen on one thing, and doing all of your hobby and sharing your expertise with the entire world while not knowing English is kind of problematic. Knowing the language of diplomats, you'll relish the works of your favorite entertainers and clearly perceive what the performer is singing regarding and what emotions he's making an attempt to convey to his fans.

During the scientific-practical conference of scholars in 2015, the subsequent knowledge were mentioned:

English is studied by virtually three hundred million Chinese (comparable to the United States of America population);

In Japan, Gymnasium students learn English for six years;

In France, Gymnasium students area unit needed to check foreign languages (German or English to settle on from). Virtually eighty fifth of scholars like learning English;

In ninety countries of the planet, English is that the second state language, or is wide studied.

In Sweden, Scandinavian country and Denmark, English is mandatory.

And another fascinating reality favors the connexion of land language within the times. Among all European countries, excluding the united kingdom and eire, The Netherlands ranks initial within the variety of individuals UN agency area unit fluent in English. In European country, students area unit offered the selection of learning English or French, and additional students area unit selecting the previous.

The role of English within the lifetime of trendy individuals

Since the twentieth century, English has been used because the language for international communication. It's in English that business negotiations area unit control, high-level conferences area unit control and vital documents area unit signed. Therefore, to grasp a world language these days isn't a whim, however a necessity for each specialist and educated person.

Proficiency in English is very vital for people who operate within the business. After all, several firms area unit actively cooperating with foreign partners. So as for dialogues with colleagues to be productive, while not employing a lexicon, it's value taking time to be told English. Additionally, sensible command of the language makes it attainable to convert foreign partners, demonstrating to them their seriousness in doing business.

The role of a remote language within the times is absolutely nice. At a similar time, English isn't a language that different languages of the planet try to exchange - it's solely a good addition. Taking under consideration the very fact that the planet is consistently up, and all told directions (technology, business, IT-industry and others), English has become associate degree obligatory "attribute" for each specialist in their field.

Conclusion

Summing up the role, importance and connectedness of a people language within the modern times, it's price noting the subsequent. Knowing a global language permits you to induce a lot of valuable info. Content on the net, films, music - all this can be made for the foremost half in English. Data of the language can eliminate the distortion which will be gift within the translation.

In the modern times, not knowing English virtually cuts you far from several achievements of civilization. You limit yourself to a comparatively tiny dome of knowledge and language rather than thinking a lot of globally. Again, most of the knowledge on the net is in English (more than 54%). A global language permits you to induce a good education at a prestigious university, a dream job and full communication with foreigners from any corner of the earth.